

Stigma against mental illness and mental health: The role of social media

Amelia RIZZO^{1*}, Lorena CALANDI², Monica FARANDA³,
Maria Grazia ROSANO⁴, Viviana CARLOTTA⁵, Enrica VINCI⁶

Cite this paper as: Rizzo A, Calandi L, Faranda M, Rosano MG, Carlotta V, Vinci E. Stigma against mental illness and mental health: The role of Social Media. *Adv Med Psychol Public Health*. 2025;2(2):125-130. Doi: 10.5281/zenodo.13223184

¹Department of Clinical and Experimental Medicine and Department of Cognitive Sciences, Pedagogical Psychological and Cultural Studies, University of Messina, Messina, Italy. Medical-Legal Center of the National Institute of Social Welfare, Messina, Italy. E-mail: amrizzo@unime.it ORCID: 0000-0002-6229-6463

²Medical-Legal Center of the National Institute of Social Welfare, Messina, Italy. E-mail: calandilorena@fiscali.it ORCID: 0009-0008-4683-5165

³Medical-Legal Center of the National Institute of Social Welfare, Messina, Italy. E-mail: monifaranda@gmail.com ORCID: 0009-0001-6294-9989

⁴Medical-Legal Center of the National Institute of Social Welfare, Messina, Italy. E-mail: mariagraziarosano@hotmail.it ORCID: 0009-0006-3493-7645

⁵Dermatology Clinic - Center for Dermatological and Sexually Transmitted Diseases Center, ASP-5 Messina, Italy. E-mail: viviana_carlotta@hotmail.com ORCID: 0009-0004-5994-8311

⁶Medical-Legal Center of the National Institute of Social Welfare, Messina, Italy. E-mail: enricavinci@gmail.com ORCID: 0009-0002-1080-9973

*Correspondence

Abstract

This paper investigates the pervasive stigma against mental illness and mental health, emphasizing the role of social media in shaping public attitudes and perceptions. Stigma, historically rooted in negative attitudes and discriminatory practices, continues to pose significant barriers for individuals with mental disorders. The article highlights various forms of prejudice, including those against mental illness, and examines the cultural, personal, and experiential factors contributing to these biases. The concept of stigma is dissected to reveal its cognitive, affective, and behavioral components, as well as its historical origins and contemporary implications. Social media serves as a double-edged sword in this context: it can foster supportive communities and reduce stigma through shared personal experiences and increased awareness, yet it also risks perpetuating harmful stereotypes and misinformation. The dual impact of social media is analyzed, showing its potential to both alleviate and exacerbate feelings of social isolation, loneliness, and inadequacy, particularly among vulnerable populations. The study discusses the negative effects of idealized representations, negative social comparisons, and cyberbullying, which can amplify anxiety, depression, and self-stigma. Conversely, social media can offer a platform for positive change, encouraging open discussions and mutual support. Concluding, the paper underscores the need for continuous public education, challenging harmful stereotypes, and fostering inclusive environments. Addressing the misconceptions propagated through social media is crucial in reducing stigma and promoting a compassionate, empathetic approach to mental health.

Take-home message: Addressing mental health stigma is vital for a compassionate society. This commentary underscores the impact of prejudice and social media on public perceptions. Researchers should explore targeted interventions and regional stigma variations, while policymakers need strategies to combat discrimination and utilize social media for positive change.

Keywords: Mental illness; mental health; prejudice; social media; stigma.

INTRODUCTION

In social psychology, prejudice is a negative attitude toward a person belonging to a specific social group or a condition that is assumed to influence interpersonal relationships negatively [1]. Prejudice can take various forms: (a) Ethnic prejudice [2]; (b) Sexism [3]; (c) Sexual prejudice (homophobia) [4]; (d) Ageism [5]; (e) Prejudice against people with obesity [6]; (f) Prejudice against individuals with mental disorders [7]; (g) Prejudice against physically disabled people [8].

The causes of prejudices and stereotypes may be traced back to cultural factors (dominance of a conservative and authoritarian viewpoint), personal factors (lack of empathy and inability to engage), and past experiences (negative relationships with individuals with mental disorders) [9,10]. Prejudice arises a priori, even before knowing or directly interacting with a person. As an attitude, prejudice includes a cognitive component (stereotype), an affective component (emotions arising from a specific civil context), and a behavioral component (intentions of group members leading to discrimination) [11,12].

This commentary aims to explore the various forms of prejudice, analyze the causes and consequences of the stigma associated with mental disorders, and discuss the impact of social media on public perception of mental health.

DISCUSSION

In Greek, stigma can be defined as a sort of "*mark*" or "*sign*" that the ancient Greeks used to distinguish slaves from free men. The Greeks introduced the term "stigma" to highlight, through physical signs, a deplorable condition of the personality of those who bore them [13]. These marks were incised with a knife or burned into the skin to clarify that the marked person has to be excluded, deprecated, and not socially accepted.

In social psychiatry, the term stigma refers to a set of negative factors associated with individuals with a mental disorder. Specifically, according to the World Health Organization, stigma represents "*a mark of shame, disgrace, or disapproval that leads to rejection, discrimination, and exclusion from social contexts and situations.*" [14,15].

Stigma related to mental health issues is prevalent in collective thinking, widespread, and difficult to modify. Common behaviors among people include fear of interacting with individuals with psychological issues due to their perceived unpredictability and reluctance to assign important roles to them because they are considered unreliable [16]. These situations inevitably cause additional suffering to those affected, adding to an already acute state of distress. These individuals face a dual conflict: awareness of being "ill" and thus differently abled and being targets of stigmatized stereotypes, exacerbating their distress and leading to greater exclusion and discrimination, resulting in an increasing vulnerability [17].

This results in the "internalized stigma," where the individual convinces themselves that societal prejudices about them are true, resulting in self-perceptions like "I have depression *because I am lazy.*" This attitude is linked to very low self-esteem and a lack of recognition of one's abilities, leading to thoughts like "*I am worthless,*" "*I am a failure,*" and "*no one will ever trust me with an important task.*" [18]. In this vicious cycle, the psychiatric patient is less likely to seek specialized care for fear of confirming the "crazy" and "hopelessness" label assigned by society [19].

Stigma in healthcare systems

An aspect not to be underestimated is "*diagnostic overshadowing*," the underestimation of physical ailments in people with mental disorders [20]. Often, psychiatric patients seeking medical help for any health issues separate from their mental problems are quickly dismissed by healthcare providers who attribute the physical condition to the mental disorder, rendering their complaints less credible. Discrimination occurs from the triage stage, where they receive little attention and wait long before being attended to.

In parallel, *overprotective behavior* develops. Healthcare providers, considering the patient incapable of understanding, make decisions for them, surpassing supportive attitudes and leading to patient passivity, making them feel like a child. Another significant aspect is "*protective benevolence*," where doctors' overly accommodating behavior to maintain the patient's psychological balance can be perceived as disrespectful and dishonest [21]. The patient feels deceived by promises of something in exchange for accepting therapy, only to find these promises unmet.

Regarding mental health issues, two aspects must be considered: psychological difficulty and psychiatric disability. In both cases, the individual faces inhibition in achieving their goals serenely and a discriminative situation due to ongoing external prejudices. Concepts like self-stigma and social prejudice prevent these individuals from living without issues and represent enormous barriers to overcome [22].

Historically, these individuals' lives were heavily influenced by social prejudices, leading to increasingly acute discrimination [23]. To prevent individuals with mental disorders from facing continuous restrictions, it is essential to limit prejudice related to these specific issues. Understanding the causes of stigma, eliminating the idea that people with mental disorders pose a societal threat [24], and abolishing commonly used terminology to describe mental disorders are necessary.

Stigma and social media

The representation of mental disorders on social media is a topic of growing interest and debate, reflecting the evolution of our understanding and approach to mental health issues in modern society [25]. Social media platforms play a powerful role in informing, raising awareness, and influencing public perceptions of mental disorders.

On the one hand, they provide an unprecedented platform for sharing personal experiences, reducing stigma, and promoting mutual support among individuals facing similar challenges [26-29].

On the other hand, there is a risk that these platforms can spread misleading information, harmful stereotypes, and sensationalistic or sanitized representations, negatively impacting public perception and affecting individuals' well-being [30].

Constant exposure to social media can have both positive and negative repercussions on individual mental health. Recent literature has shown that social media use can amplify feelings of isolation and loneliness, especially when virtual connections replace face-to-face interactions, leaving individuals without the emotional support and warmth that real relationships offer. This isolation can be exacerbated in those already suffering from mental disorders, making it more challenging for them to seek help or connect with others in meaningful ways [31].

Additionally, the often curated and idealized nature of life presented on social media can distort users' perception of reality, leading to negative social comparisons, personal dissatisfaction, and increased feelings of inadequacy. These dynamics can exacerbate conditions of anxiety and depression, especially among young people and adolescents who are particularly sensitive to social pressures and self-image [32].

Pathological online behaviors, such as cyberbullying or the spread of harmful content, can also stem from unexpressed inner distress or sadistic tendencies. These acts not only harm the victims but also reflect and reinforce the disturbed mental state of the perpetrators, creating a vicious cycle of negativity and suffering [33]. Without appropriate intervention measures, such as content moderation and psychological support, social media can become an echo chamber for these behaviors, exacerbating problems instead of providing a way out [34].

The pressure to maintain a perfect public image can also induce stress and anxiety, leading individuals to hide their true struggles for fear of judgment or not meeting perceived standards. This masking of real difficulties hinders honest and open communication about mental well-being, hampering efforts to raise awareness and reduce the stigma associated with mental disorders [35-40].

CONCLUSION

The stigmatization of mental health issues remains pervasive despite advancements in understanding and awareness. Reducing stigma requires continuous efforts to educate and inform the public, challenge harmful stereotypes, and promote inclusive and supportive environments for those affected by mental disorders [41,42]. Addressing the prejudices and misconceptions perpetuated by social media and other platforms is crucial in this endeavor, as is fostering a more compassionate and empathetic society that values mental health as much as physical health. For this reason, policymakers should develop targeted strategies to combat mental health discrimination and leverage social media as a tool for positive change.

Author Contributions: Conceptualization: A.R.; Resources: L.C., M.F., V.C.; writing—original draft preparation: A.R.; review and editing: M.G.R. E.V.

All the authors have read and agreed to the published version of the manuscript.

Acknowledgments: None

Conflicts of Interest: The authors declare no conflict of interest.

Disclaimer/Publisher's Note: The Publisher remains neutral regarding jurisdictional claims in published maps and institutional affiliations. Additionally, the Publisher is not responsible for the accuracy, completeness, or validity of the content of scientific articles published herein. This statement exempts the Publisher from any responsibility regarding the content of scientific articles, which is solely the responsibility of the authors and peer reviewers.

References

1. Duckitt JH. The social psychology of prejudice. New York: Praeger; 1992 Jun 16.
2. Zick A, Pettigrew TF, Wagner U. Ethnic prejudice and discrimination in Europe. *J Soc Issues*. 2008 Jun;64(2):233-251.
3. Ahmed S. Introduction: Sexism-A problem with a name. <https://journals.lwbooks.co.uk/newformations/vol-2015-issue-86/abstract-8658/>. Accessed 15 March 2024.
4. Herek GM. Beyond “homophobia”: Thinking about sexual prejudice and stigma in the twenty-first century. *Sex Res Soc Policy*. 2004 Apr;1:6-24.
5. Nelson TD. *Handbook of Prejudice, Stereotyping, and Discrimination*. New York: Psychology Press; 2009.
6. Puhl R, Brownell KD. Bias, discrimination, and obesity. *Obes Res*. 2001 Dec;9(12):788-805. doi: 10.1038/oby.2001.108.
7. Rössler W. The stigma of mental disorders: A millennia-long history of social exclusion and prejudices. *EMBO Rep*. 2016 Sep;17(9):1250-1253.
8. Dovidio JF, Pagotto L, Hebl MR. Implicit attitudes and discrimination against people with physical disabilities. In: Wiener RL, Willborn SL (Eds.). *Disability and aging discrimination: Perspectives in law and psychology* Springer Science + Business Media; 2011, pp. 157–183. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4419-6293-5_9.
9. Fiske ST. Stereotyping, prejudice, and discrimination at the seam between the centuries: Evolution, culture, mind, and brain. *Eur J Soc Psychol*. 2000 May;30(3):299-322.
10. Ekehammar B, Akrami N, Gylje M, Zakrisson I. What matters most to prejudice: Big five personality, social dominance orientation, or right-wing authoritarianism? *Eur J Personality*. 2004 Sep;18(6):463-482.

11. Aronson J, Burgess D, Phelan SM, Juarez L. Unhealthy interactions: the role of stereotype threat in health disparities. *Am J Public Health*. 2013 Jan;103(1):50-56. doi: 10.2105/AJPH.2012.300828. Epub 2012 Nov 15.
12. Amodio DM. The neuroscience of prejudice and stereotyping. *Nat Rev Neurosci*. 2014 Oct;15(10):670-682. doi: 10.1038/nrn3800. Epub 2014 Sep 4.
13. Tzouvara V, Papadopoulos C, Randhawa G. Systematic review of the prevalence of mental illness stigma within the Greek culture. *Int J Soc Psychiatr*. 2016 May;62(3):292-305.
14. Mann CE, Himelein MJ. Factors associated with stigmatization of persons with mental illness. *Psychiatr Serv*. 2004 Feb;55(2):185-187.
15. Hinshaw SP, Stier A. Stigma as related to mental disorders. *Annu Rev Clin Psychol*. 2008 Apr 27;4:367-393.
16. Östman M, Kjellin L. Stigma by association: psychological factors in relatives of people with mental illness. *Br J Psychiatry*. 2002 Dec;181(6):494-498.
17. Ben-Zeev D, Young MA, Corrigan PW. DSM-V and the stigma of mental illness. *J Ment Health*. 2010 Aug 1;19(4):318-327.
18. Picco L, Pang S, Lau YW, Jeyagurunathan A, Satghare P, Abidin E, et al. Internalized stigma among psychiatric outpatients: Associations with quality of life, functioning, hope and self-esteem. *Psychiatry Res*. 2016 Dec 30;246:500-506.
19. Szcześniak D, Kobylko A, Wojciechowska I, Kłapciński M, Rymaszewska J. Internalized stigma and its correlates among patients with severe mental illness. *Neuropsychiatr Dis Treat*. 2018 Oct 8;2599-2608.
20. Hallyburton A. Diagnostic overshadowing: an evolutionary concept analysis on the misattribution of physical symptoms to pre-existing psychological illnesses. *Int J Ment Health Nurs*. 2022 Dec;31(6):1360-1372.
21. Thornicroft G, Rose D, Kassam A. Discrimination in health care against people with mental illness. *Int Rev Psychiatry*. 2007 Jan 1;19(2):113-122.
22. Corrigan P. How stigma interferes with mental health care. *Am Psychol*. 2004 Oct;59(7):614-625.
23. Rüsç N, Corrigan PW, Todd AR, Bodenhausen GV. Automatic stereotyping against people with schizophrenia, schizoaffective and affective disorders. *Psychiatry Res*. 2011 Mar 30;186(1):34-39.
24. Rössler W. The stigma of mental disorders: A millennia-long history of social exclusion and prejudices. *EMBO Rep*. 2016 Sep;17(9):1250-1253.
25. Aragon M, Monroy AP, Gonzalez L, Losada DE, Montes M. DisorBERT. A Double Domain Adaptation Model for Detecting Signs of Mental Disorders in Social Media. In: *Proceedings of the 61st Annual Meeting of the Association for Computational Linguistics (Volume 1: Long Papers)* 2023 Jul, pp. 15305-15318.
26. Rizzo A, Alparone D. Surfing Alone: From Internet Addiction to the Era of Smartphone Dependence. *Int J Environ Res Public Health*. 2024 Apr 3;21(4):436.
27. Rizzo A, Batra K, Yıldırım M, Tordonato G, De Maio V, Khabbache H, et al. Social Media: Stress Factors or Coping Strategies? A Pilot Study in a Sample of Italian Teachers. *Iran Rehabil J*. 2024;22(2):333-344.
28. Akbağ M, Aydoğdu F, Rizzo A. A New Measure of the Parental Phubbing-Mother and Father Form for Turkish Adolescents: Evaluation of Validity and Reliability, 08 May 2024, PREPRINT (Version 1) available at Research Square. <https://doi.org/10.21203/rs.3.rs-4378909/v1>.
29. Manap A, Rizzo A, Yıldırım A, Dilekçi Ü, Yıldırım M. The mediating role of procrastination in the relationship between fear of missing out and internet addiction in university students. *Int J Environ Res Public Health*. 2023 Dec 29;21(1):49.
30. Naslund JA, Deng D. Addressing mental health stigma in low-income and middle-income countries: a new frontier for digital mental health. *Ethics Med Public Health*. 2021 Dec 1;19:100719.

31. Çağış ZG, Öztekin GG, Aziz IA, Chirico F, Rizzo A, Yıldırım M. Meaning in Life and Loneliness as Mediators between COVID-19 Anxiety and Life Satisfaction in the Post-Pandemic among the General Population in Turkey: A Serial Mediation Model. *Eur J Investig Health Psychol Educ*. 2023 Oct 9;13(10):2214-2225.
32. Orben A, Meier A, Dalgleish T, Blakemore SJ. Mechanisms linking social media use to adolescent mental health vulnerability. *Nat Rev Psychol*. 2024 May 7:1-7.
33. Rizzo A, Princiotta E, Iuele G. Exploring the link between smartphone use, recorded violence, and social sharing in 80 case studies in Italy. *Psych*. 2023 Dec 14;5(4):1241-1255.
34. Rizzo A, Della Villa L, Crisi A. Can the Problematic Internet Use evolve in a pre-psychotic state? A single case study with the Wartegg. *Comput Human Behav*. 2015 Oct 1;51:532-538.
35. Nicita E, Bruno F, Rizzo A. *Oltre lo stigma verso la psicoterapia. Teorie, ricerche, soluzioni*. New York: Barnes & Noble Press; 2023. ISBN: 9798855618440.
36. Rizzo A, Gatto E, Calandi L, Alfa R. *Embodied Online Therapy*. Nova Science Publishers; 2024. ISBN: 9798891135376.
37. Tarchi L, Castellini G, Ricca V. Zipf's law: Divergence from general content in online affected communities of peers by deficit/hyperactivity attention disorder (ADHD) and anorexia nervosa. *Adv Med Psychol Public Health*. 2024;1(2):82-91. doi: 10.5281/zenodo.10637481.
38. Rizzo A, Alfa R, Piccolo MC, Giuffrida A, Spina GS, Currò V, et al. Binge eating and personality traits: A gender-specific analysis among patients affected by obesity. *Adv Med Psychol Public Health*. 2024;1(1):6-11. doi: 10.5281/zenodo.10597085.
39. Finistrella M, Flores P, Frediani G. Animal-assisted therapy in patients affected by schizophrenia and schizophrenic-related disorders: A scoping review. *Adv Med Psychol Public Health*. 2024;1(2):53-61. doi: 10.5281/zenodo.10632991.
40. Gharib M, Borhaninejad V, Rashedi V. Mental health challenges among older adults. *Adv Med Psychol Public Health*. 2024;1(3):106-107. doi: 10.5281/zenodo.10899226.
41. Chirico F, Khabbache H, Rizzo A, Nucera G, Yıldırım M, Batra K, et al. Bridging ethics and spirituality in healthcare policies for a holistic response to climate change, new pandemics, and global health challenges: A call to action. *Adv Med Psychol Public Health*. 2024;1(4):170-173. doi: 10.5281/zenodo.11068942.
42. Khabbache H, Ouazizi K, Ait Ali D, Cherqui A, Rizzo A, Tarchi L, et al. Cultural Placebos from the Wild in Patients With Mental Disorders: The Case of The Nour Association in Fez-Morocco. *Iran Rehabil J*. 2024 Mar 10;22(1):129-138.

Copyright: © 2025 by the authors. Submitted for possible open-access publication under the terms and conditions of the Creative Commons Attribution (CC BY) license (<https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>).